

Serum Ferritin Levels and Complications in Beta Thalassaemia Patients

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Abstract— Beta thalassaemia is a hereditary blood disorder characterized by reduced or absent production of beta globin chains, leading to anemia and potential complications from iron overload. Chelation therapy stands as a cornerstone for the survival of patients with beta thalassaemia. Prior to commencing chelation therapy, it is imperative to thoroughly investigate the complications associated with iron overload. Our study focused to discover the complications raised due to iron overloading, which significantly affect the health of patient and for the initiation of iron chelation therapy. This was a Prospective Observational study with 100 patients of Beta thalassaemia. There were 53 males and 47 females Beta Thalassaemia patients. The mean age of study population was 10±5.29 years. The high serum ferritin levels were observed in males compared to females. Splenomegaly was observed in 28 out of 100 beta thalassaemia patients in which 22 were female and 6 were male. Hepatomegaly was observed in 14 out of 100 beta thalassaemia patients in which all 14 were female, majority of them were from age group 1-5 and 6-10 years. There was no overall significant difference of serum ferritin levels in the study population during the study period. The complications such as hepatomegaly, splenomegaly diabetes mellitus and impaired fasting glycemia has been observed in the patients having high serum ferritin levels. The initiation of iron chelation therapy was necessary as to avoid the further complications. Further studies involving the multiple centres and a greater number of patients are required to substantiate the results of the present study.

Keywords— Thalassaemia, Chelation therapy, Serum ferritin, Iron over dose, Splenomegaly,

1. Introduction

Thalassaemia arises from a hereditary blood condition wherein insufficient production of the protein haemoglobin occurs, a crucial component of red blood cells.[1] This disorder manifests in two primary forms: Alpha and Beta Thalassaemia, with Beta Thalassaemia being the more severe variant.[2] Beta Thalassaemia is primarily attributed to mutations in the haemoglobin gene (HBB).[3]

Individuals born with thalassaemia typically encounter health complications within months of birth. The primary health concerns linked to thalassaemia include anemia, characterized by profound fatigue, weakness, shortness of breath, palpitations, irregular heartbeats, pale skin, and iron overload.[4]

Thalassaemia patients may experience chronic iron overload due to both regular blood transfusions and excessive absorption of iron in the gastrointestinal tract, Iron overload can lead to further serious complications as the body lacks a mechanism to eliminate the excess iron.[5]

Chelation therapy stands as a cornerstone for the survival of patients with beta thalassemia.[6] Its primary objective is to avert the buildup of excessive iron and the consequent serious complications associated with it.[7]

Prior to commencing chelation therapy, it is imperative to thoroughly investigate the complications associated with iron overload.[8] This comprehensive understanding of the potential risks and outcomes of iron accumulation enables healthcare providers to make well-informed decisions regarding the initiation and management of chelation therapy in beta thalassemia patients.[8] The primary method used to assess iron overload is by measuring serum ferritin levels.[9]

Our study focused to discover the complications raised due to iron overloading, which significantly affect the health of patient and for the initiation of iron chelation therapy. Active evaluation and prevention of these complications can prevent risk of mortality of patient.

2.METHOD:

This was a Prospective observational study with 100 Patients with Beta thalassemia major children between 3 to 17 years, registered in red cross society hospital, being regularly transfused at department of Paediatrics, Indian red cross society hospital, Eluru, AP.

This study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee. Prior to the subject Enrollment, all the subjects were briefed about the purpose of the study and written informed consent was obtained from the legally authorized representative of the patient. All investigations were done free of cost and no financial burden was imposed on the patient.

The objectives of this study were to evaluate the complications arrived with high levels of serum ferritin and glycaemic abnormalities in beta thalassemia patients during study period.

Patients were recruited from January 2019–December 2019. The study population included patients of either gender aged about 3-17 years with evidence of Beta Thalassemia major children who has been admitted in the red cross Society, diagnosed with iron overload, patients who have pre-haemoglobin levels, having complications like splenomegaly. Patients not having any growth changes, aged <1 year and not having iron overload were excluded from the study. Patients who did not give informed written consent were also excluded.

Detailed history (age, sex, history of blood transfusion, history of iron-chelation therapy) was taken from the patient and 3ml of blood was collected by vein puncture and allowed to clot. The serum was separated from collected blood and used for the estimation of ferritin levels using ELISA based serum ferritin assay

kit (Aciculate ferritin kit) by chemiluminescence immunoassay method. The serum ferritin values were observed in patients on 3rd, 6th and 9th months.

Patients with known history of Beta Thalassemia who met the inclusion criteria were evaluated with a comprehensive clinical history, detailed physical examination, and relevant investigations include Serum ferritin levels, Haemoglobin, fasting and postprandial blood sugar and other investigations such as Ultrasound to measure spleen size and liver size were done.

While evaluating the complications, haemoglobin was measured from the collected blood. Diabetes and Pre-Diabetes was considered when patients were diagnosed as per the American diabetic association guidelines. Hepatomegaly and splenomegaly were considered when the patient spleen and liver size, observed by Ultrasound image is more than the normal size.

statistical analysis for the serum ferritin levels was done using ANOVA. A P value<0.05 was taken as significant. Haemoglobin and BMI between the genders was assessed by Z-test. ANOVA was done to estimate the difference in serum ferritin levels on 3rd month, 6th month and 9th month. The statistical software namely SPSS and Effect Size calculator were used for the analysis of the data. GraphPad Prism 8.0.1 have been used to generate graphs and Microsoft Word and Excel have been used to generate tables.

3.Results

In the present study, 100 patients of Beta thalassemia major children who met inclusion criteria were assessed for complications arrived with high levels of serum ferritin and glycaemic abnormalities in beta thalassemia patients during study period. The age and sex distribution among the beta thalassemia patients were depicted in table I. There were 53 males and 47 females Beta Thalassemia patients in our study. Among them, majority were females of age group 1-5 years(n=25).

Table I Age and sex distribution in Beta Thalassemia Patients

Age group(years)	Males	Females	Total
1-5	0	25	25
6-10	9	22	31
11-15	22	0	22
15-20	19	0	19
21-25	3	0	3
Total	53	47	100

The mean age of study population was 10±5.29 years. There was no statistically significant(P=0.199) difference in the Haemoglobin of the patients with respect to gender. The mean BMI of females was 16.1kg/m², males was 15.7 kg/m² and BMI for total patients was 15.9 kg/m². There was no statistically significant(P=0.4) difference in the Body Mass Index (BMI) of the patients respective to gender. The mean serum ferritin levels were depicted in table II.

Among them highest mean of serum ferritin (3689.8) was observed in males on 3rd month. Out of 100 patients, impaired Fasting Glucose was observed in 11 patients accounts for 11% and Diabetes mellitus was observed in 5 patients which accounts for 5%. The patients with impaired fasting glucose and diabetes mellitus based on age were represented in figure 1.

Table II Mean serum ferritin levels of the patients

Months	Serum ferritin values (Mean)		
	Female(n=47)(mean)	Male(n=53)(mean)	Total(n=100)
3 months	3151.765957	3689.75472	3436.9
6 months	3020.744681	3465.0566	3256.23
9 months	2503	3159.39623	2850.89

Splenomegaly was observed in 28 out of 100 beta thalassemia patients in which 22 were female and 6 were male, the age and splenomegaly values of patients were represented in figure1. The complications were observed more in female patients compared to males and mostly observed in the age group 1-5 years in our study.

There was statistically significant($P=<0.0001$) difference in the difference in Spleen size among the patients which was depicted in Table III.

Table III Complications observed during the study period

Factor	Mean±SD	Number	P Value
HB	7.703±1.263349	100	0.1992*
BMI	15.878±2.34 kg/m ²	100	0.397*
Fasting glucose value	117.82±3.43	11	-
Random glucose	139.6±2.97	5	-
Spleen Size	4.07±2.6	28	<0.0001*
Liver size	4.18±2.2	14	0.6263*

*-Z-Test * -T-test,

Hepatomegaly was observed in 14 out of 100 beta thalassemia patients in which all 14 were female, majority of them were from age group 1-5 and 6-10 years and the liver size and age of patients with hepatomegaly were represented in figure 1.

Figure 1: a) Splenomegaly values in beta thalassemia patients, b) Hepatomegaly values in Beta Thalassemia Patients, c) Impaired fasting glycemia patients of beta thalassemia, d) Diabetes mellitus patients of beta thalassemia.

There was no statistically significant(P=0.63) difference in the difference in Liver size among the patients and same was depicted in Table III.

There was no statistically significant difference in serum ferritin levels among the 3rd, 6th and 9th month in females(P=0.18), males(P=0.4) and in total study population(P=0.1) and the same data was depicted in table IV.

Table IV Serum ferritin values observed in the 3rd, 6th and 9th months

Serum ferritin values	ANOVA		Chi-square test	
	F value	P value	χ ²	P value
Female	1.76207	0.1758	13.1054	0.0014
Male	0.89828	0.409252	0.327988	0.848747
Total	2.2802	0.104051	3.04109	0.218593

4. Discussion

Beta thalassemia is a hereditary blood disorder characterized by reduced or absent production of beta globin chains, leading to anemia and potential complications from iron overload.

The evaluation of the complications arrived with high levels of serum ferritin and glycaemic abnormalities in beta thalassemia patients during study period. There were 53 male and 47 female were there in the study.

The high serum ferritin levels were observed in males compared to females. A similar observation was found in previous study done by Ling-ling Han et al.[10]

The BMI has been affected with the increase in the serum ferritin levels in children.[11] In our 5% of the study population has experienced diabetes mellitus, A similar observation was found in previous study i.e., the study done by Ahmed saleh et al. where in 6.5% of study population was found to be diabetes mellitus.[12]

About 11% of the study population has experienced impaired fasting glycaemic levels, which was also supported by study done by Nazan Erenoglu Son which shows that there was strong relation between high serum ferritin levels and impaired fasting glycemia.[13]

About 14% of the study population have experienced hepatomegaly which differs from the study done by the Muhammad shujat ali, 44% of his study population has experienced hepatomegaly.[14]

In β -thalassaemia patients lacking co-factors, fibrosis typically develops when the hepatic iron concentration exceeds approximately 16 mg/g dry weight liver. Clinical research indicates a correlation between hepatic iron concentration and the onset of iron-induced hepatotoxicity.[15],[16]

Splenomegaly was observed 28% of the population, A similar observation was found in previous studies i.e., the study by Souvik Basak.[17] Individuals with beta thalassemia may experience spleen enlargement due to heightened red blood cell destruction, extramedullary hematopoiesis (the formation of blood cells outside the bone marrow), frequent blood transfusions, or iron accumulation.[18]

Our study had limitations include it was conducted in a small group of patients, the number blood transfusions of the patients have not been observed and long-term follow-up of patients was not done. Only few complications were evaluated in our study.

5. CONCLUSIONS

There was no overall significant difference of serum ferritin levels in the study population during the study period. The complications such as hepatomegaly, splenomegaly diabetes mellitus and impaired fasting glycemia has been observed in the patients having high serum ferritin levels. The initiation of iron chelation therapy was necessary as to avoid the further complications. Further studies involving the multiple centres and a greater number of patients are required to substantiate the results of the present study.

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